

ANISOGRID COMPOSITE LATTICE FLOOR BEAM STRUCTURES FOR COMMERCIAL AIRPLANES

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ABSTRACT

The paper is concerned with development of Anisogrid (Anisotropic Grid) thin-walled lattice beams consisting of a system of helical, hoop and axial ribs made of unidirectional carbon-epoxy composite material by continuous filament winding.

Anisogrid composite lattice beams with rectangular cross sections can be used in aircraft structures as fuselage floor beams providing high weight saving in comparison with aluminum prototypes. In application to a typical single-aisle commercial airplane fuselage, the structure, and design of a lattice composite box beam is considered. The beam analysis is undertaken on the basis of the applied theory of thin-walled composite beams, the governing equations of which are presented. Fabrication and testing of an experimental 4m long floor beam are described and discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are widely used now in airframe structures of commercial airplanes mainly within the framework of the traditional stringer stiffened design concept based on the idea of the load-carrying skin, whereas the ribs provide the proper bending stiffness and resistance to buckling under compression and shear. It is important that in composite stiffened structures the skin and the ribs are not unidirectional and have a laminated structure consisting of composite plies with various orientation angles. The efficient mechanical characteristics of such laminates are considerably lower than the corresponding longitudinal properties of unidirectional composite materials. Particularly, the modulus of a widely used quasi-isotropic carbon-epoxy laminate is less than modulus of aluminum.

In contrast to stringer structures, in anisogrid composite lattice structures, the main load-carrying elements are the ribs. It is important that the ribs are made by continuous filament winding and have a unidirectional structure demonstrating high specific (with respect to density) material strength and stiffness. Anisogrid composite fuselage section of Russian IL-114 short-range airplane built in CRISM in 1986 is shown in Fig.1. As can be seen, the fuselage has traditional aluminum floor beams supported with struts. Recently, thin-walled lattice composite beams demonstrated in Fig.2. have been developed for space applications. In application to commercial airplanes, such structures can be used as fuselage floor beams. Possessing high stiffness and weight efficiency, they do not require traditional struts which can penetrate into the passenger cabin in the event of the airplane crash and limit the space of the cargo section [1].

This paper is concerned with design, analysis, fabrication and testing of Anisogrid composite airplane floor beams.

2 DESIGN

To be specific, consider an anisogrid fuselage of a single-aisle middle-range commercial airplane (Fig.3). with cross section shown in Fig.4.

The load for which the floor beam is designed occurs in crash landing of the airplane accompanied with damage and decompression of the bottom cargo section and is simulated with the pressure p acting on the floor (Fig.4), i.e.

Figure 1: Anisogrid composite fuselage section with aluminum floor beams.

Figure 2: Anisogrid composite box beams.

Figure 3: Anisogrid composite 4m diameter fuselage section.

Figure 4: Fuselage cross section.

$$p = f \left(\Delta p + \frac{nMG}{l s_s} \right) \quad (1)$$

Here $f = 1.25$ is the safety factor, $\Delta p = 0,03$ MPa is the difference between the pressure in the passenger cabin and the cargo section, $n = 6$ is the number of passengers in the row, $M = 105$ kg is the passenger and checked luggage mass, $G = 6g$ is the vertical acceleration, $l = 3.7$ m is the beam length and $s_s = 0.76$ m is the seat pitch. Calculation with the aid of Eq.(1) yields $p = 0.054$ MPa.

The line load q acting on the beam (Fig.4) can be found as

$$q = p s_b = 20.5 \text{ kN/m} \quad (2)$$

in which $s_b = 0.38$ m is the beam pitch. Assuming that the beam is simply supported at the ends, we can determine the maximum shear force V_m and the maximum bending moment, i.e.,

$$V_m = \frac{ql}{2} = 31.9 \text{ kN}, \quad M_m = \frac{ql^2}{8} = 35.1 \text{ kN} \cdot \text{m} \quad (3)$$

To design the beam introduce the simplified model of the structure assuming that the shear force is taken by the vertical shear webs of the beam, whereas the bending moment is taken by the horizontal flanges. The cross section and the development of the beam surface are presented in Fig.5

Figure 5: Cross section (a) and development of the beam surface (b).

The shear force, V_m , is taken by two vertical shear webs 1-2 and 3-4 (Fig.5(a)) and can be expressed in terms of the stress σ_h acting in helical ribs as

$$V_m = 2k\sigma_h h\delta_h \sin \varphi_h \quad (4)$$

In which k is the number of helical ribs passing through the shear web cross section, h is the web thickness, δ_h is the thickness of the helical rib (the width of the rib cross section) and φ_h is the angle between the rib and beam axes.

Consider first parameter k . The simplest lattice structure corresponds to $k = 1$. However, this structure is not reliable, because the damage of a single rib of the shear web results in the beam failure. The larger the k number, the higher the reliability of a beam. But respectively, the more complicated are the tooling and the manufacturing process. Taking into account the real typical dimensions of the beam cross section, it is assumed that $k = 2$ as shown in Fig.5 (b). Second, consider parameters h and δ_h . A possible mode of failure of helical ribs is local buckling of the rib segment between the points of ribs intersection. Because local buckling can appear in the web plane, as well as in the direction which is orthogonal to the web plane, it is reasonable to take $\delta_h = h$, i.e. to assume that the helical rib has a square cross section. And finally, consider the angle φ_h . As known, a lattice structure provides the best performance under shear if $\varphi_h = 45^\circ$. Such ribs are shown in Fig.5(b). Thus, taking $k = 2$, $\delta_h = h$ and $\varphi_h = 45^\circ$, we can use Eq. (4) to present the strength constraint for helical ribs in the following form:

$$\sigma_h = \frac{V_m}{2\sqrt{2}h^2} \leq \bar{\sigma}_h \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_h$ is the ultimate stress of the helical rib.

The second possible form of the helical rib failure is local buckling of the rib segment between the intersection points. The corresponding critical stress is specified by the modified Euler equation. For the rib with square cross section

$$\sigma_{cr} = r \frac{\pi^2 E_h h^2}{12l_h^2} \quad (6)$$

Here, $r = 1.15$ is the empirical coefficient appearing because the rib segment is not perfectly hinged at the ends, E_h is the rib modulus and

$$l_h = \frac{a - 2c}{4 \cos \varphi_h} \quad (7)$$

for the structure in Fig.5. Here, c is the manufacturing shift which allows us to move the ribs intersection point from the corner of the beam cross-sectional contour (otherwise, the winding process results in a poor rib structure at the intersection point). Taking $\varphi_h = 45^\circ$ in Eq. (7) and using Eq. (6), we can present the buckling constraint for the helical rib in the following form:

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{2.3\pi^2 E_h h^2}{3(a - 2c)^2} \geq \sigma_h \quad (8)$$

in which σ_h is specified by Eq. (5).

Consider the beam bending and assume that the bending moment is taken by the beam flanges formed by a system of helical and longitudinal ribs (Fig.5 (b)). The maximum stress in longitudinal ribs is

$$\sigma_l = E_l \frac{M_m a}{2D} \quad (9)$$

where a is the beam height (Fig.5(a)) and

$$D = \frac{a^2}{2} \left(E_l A_l + E_h \frac{bh^2}{2a_h} \right) \quad (10)$$

is the bending stiffness depending of the rib modulus E_l and E_h , the total cross-sectional area of longitudinal ribs A_l , the width of the beam cross section b (Fig.5 (a)) and the spacing of helical ribs a_h (Fig.5 (b)). Using Eq. (9) and (10), we can present the strength constraint for longitudinal ribs as

$$M_m \leq a \bar{\sigma}_l \left(A_l + \frac{E_h bh^2}{2E_l a_h} \right) \quad (11)$$

Finally, we must introduce the stiffness constraint restricting the beam maximum deflection in flight. Assuming that six passengers are sitting and one more passenger is standing in the aisle and simulating their action on the floor beam as the uniformly distributed line load, we get

$$q_p = \frac{7M_p g s_b}{l s_s} = 0.74 \text{ kN/m}$$

in which $M_p = 80 \text{ kg}$ is the passenger mass. Then, the stiffness constraint becomes (See Section 3)

$$\frac{5q_p l^3}{384D} \left(1 + \frac{48Da_h}{E_h a l^2 h^2} \right) \leq \bar{v}_m \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{v}_m = v_m / l$ and v_m is the maximum allowable deflection of the beam. The first term in Eq.(12) corresponds to beam bending and the second term – to shear. The beam mass that must be minimized in the process of design is

$$m = 2l \left[(a + b)h \left(2 \frac{h}{a_h} \rho_h + \frac{\delta_t}{a_t} \rho_t \right) + A_l \rho_l \right] \quad (13)$$

in which ρ is the rib density.

It is obvious that the beam performance is increased with the beam height (Fig.5(a)). However, a is usually restricted by the height of the cargo section (Fig.4). so, the beam height a must take the maximum allowable value and is given. The beam width b (Fig.5(a)) follows from the symmetry of the lattice structure. As can be seen in Fig.5b for the structure under consideration, $b = 0.6a$. Thus,

only two design variables, i.e., h , and A_l enter the constraints in Eqs.(5), (8), (11) and (12). The third unknown variable – the thickness of transverse ribs δ_t enters only the expression for the beam mass (13). Transverse ribs increase the critical stress for the helical ribs and provide the stiffness of the beam cross-sectional contour. However the width of these ribs, as follows from Eq.(13), must be as small as possible to give the minimum weight.

As an application, consider a typical beam with dimensions $a = 150\text{mm}$, $b = 0.6a$ and $c = 0.1$ made of carbon-epoxy composite with HTS carbon fibers. Material properties of the ribs are as follows: modulus $E_h = E_l = 94\text{ GPa}$, strength under tension and compression $\bar{\sigma}^+ = 1450\text{ MPa}$, $\bar{\sigma}^- = 650\text{ MPa}$, density $\rho_h = \rho_l = 1450\text{ kg/m}^3$. Because $\bar{\sigma}^- < \bar{\sigma}^+$, we must take $\bar{\sigma}_h < \bar{\sigma}_l = 650\text{ MPa}$ in Eq. (5) and (11). The allowable normalized deflection in Eq.(12) is $\bar{v}_m = 0.002$. The minimum width of transverse ribs is $\delta_t = 2\text{mm}$. The results of design are presented in Fig.6.

Figure 6. Design of the lattice floor beam.

Active constraints correspond to the strength conditions for helical ribs in Eq.(5) (line 1) and longitudinal ribs in Eq.(11) (line 2). The point of intersection A specifies the optimal design parameters $h = 4.6\text{ mm}$ and $A_l = 350\text{ mm}^2$. The straight line passing through point A is plotted in accordance with Eq.(13) and corresponds to the minimum beam mass $m = 5.43\text{ kg}$. Buckling and stiffness constraints in Eq.(8) and (12) are not active and are shown by dashed lines 3 and 4. Dividing A_l on the flange thickness h , we can find the total width of longitudinal ribs which is 76 mm. As follows from Fig. 5(b), the flange has 4 longitudinal ribs. Thus, the width of such longitudinal rib is $\delta_h = 19\text{ mm}$.

3 ANALYSIS

Consider the problem of transverse bending of a lattice composite floor beam with rectangular cross section (Fig.5(a)). Using the equations of the theory of thin-walled composite beams, [2] we arrive at the following expressions for the beam stiffnesses:

– bending stiffness

$$D = \frac{a^2}{4} \left(2bB_f + \frac{a}{3}B_w \right)$$

in which the stiffness coefficients of the beam flanges (index «f») and shear webs (index «w») are

$$B_f = h \left(2E_h \frac{\delta_h}{a_h} \cos^4 \varphi + E_l h \frac{\delta_l}{a_l} \right), \quad B_w = 2E_h h \frac{\delta_h}{a_h} \cos^4 \varphi$$

– transverse shear stiffness

$$S = 4E_h b h \frac{\delta_h}{a_h} \sin^2 \varphi \cos^2 \varphi$$

– torsional stiffness

$$D_t = \frac{4E_h a^2 b^2 h}{(a+b)} \frac{\delta_h}{a_h} \sin^2 \varphi \cos^2 \varphi$$

The stress in longitudinal ribs of the flanges is

$$\sigma_l^f = \pm E_l \frac{M(x)}{2D} a$$

Here signs «+» and «-» correspond to the lower and the upper flanges, M is the bending moment acting in the beam cross section $x = \text{const}$ and x is the axial coordinate. The maximum stresses in the helical ribs of the shear webs is

$$\sigma_h^w = \pm \frac{V(x) a_h a}{8h \delta_h \sin \varphi \cos \varphi} (bB_f + aB_w)$$

Here, signs «+» and «-» correspond to the ribs with angles $+\varphi$ and $-\varphi$ and $V(x)$ is the shear force acting in the beam cross section $x=\text{const}$. The rotation angle and the beam deflection can be found from the following equations

$$\theta'(x) = \frac{M(x)}{D}, \quad v(x) = \frac{V(x)}{S} - \theta \quad (14)$$

4 EXPERIMENTAL BEAM

To support the design, the experimental floor beam has been fabricated and tested. The beam parameters are as follows: $a = 80$ mm, $b = 50$ mm, $\varphi = 45^\circ$, $h = 4$ mm, $\delta_h = 4$ mm, $a_h = 21.5$ mm, $\delta_l = 2$ mm, $a_l = 15.2$ mm. The beam flanges are monopolistic ($a_l = \delta_l$ in Fig.5(b)). Material mechanical properties are $E_h = 90$ GPa, $E_l = 70$ GPa, $\bar{\sigma}^- = 600$ MPa.

The beam is fabricated by wet filament winding in the process of which impregnated carbon tows are placed into the groves formed in the elastic coating which covers the mandrel (Fig.7)

Figure 7: Winding of the lattice floor beam.

After winding, the beam is cured the mandrel is removed and the elastic coating is separated from the ribs. The fabricated beam is shown in Fig.8.

Figure 8: Experimental lattice composite floor beam

The beam is tested under three point bending. The predicted and experimental dependences of the maximum beam deflection on the applied force are shown in Fig.9.

Fig.9 Dependence of the beam maximum deflection on the applied force

- - experimental
- - analytical prediction according to Eq. (14)
- - finite-element prediction

As can be seen, calculated results are in good agreement with experiment.

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